

INNOVATIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT, HISTORY TEACHING, IMPROVED PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS.

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Annotation: High-tech technology and high speed can be used as a channel for the modern development of human society. The achievements of the world community in the field of science, technology, production, service and technology, in turn, require determining the directions of social, economic and cultural development of independent Uzbekistan. Therefore, in the conditions of globalization, the national state can remain autonomous, and this situation means that Uzbekistan needs to follow the principle of equality, cooperation and cooperation with the world community.

In these days, when special attention is being paid to the effective and purposeful use of human capital, a tendency to identify the most talented person and improve human skills has been formed on a global scale. At the same time, the problem of demography and the criticism of the natural economy are growing, the positive approach emphasizes that economic capital is a decisive factor of economic growth and national development.

The formula "Quality education - qualified specialist - national success" is an important part of the social dialectic of society. In addition, the leading state has developed its own concept for the future development of the education system, which defines the directions, important ideas and fundamental principles that guarantee revolutionary changes in the world.

Key words: improvement of history teaching methodology, "Cluster", "Bingo", "FCMU", "Boomerang", "SWOT-analysis", priority principle, educational

environment, innovative educational environment, death teaching, history teaching, history teaching methodology, improvement of history teaching methodology.

INTRODUCTION: In the year of independence, improving the quality and efficiency of education in Uzbekistan was recognized as a priority goal of our country. thereby ensuring consistent implementation of reforms. In addition, the existence of a provocative idea that defines global differences and national religiosity is becoming clear. That is why Sh.M. Mirziyoev "From national recovery to the beginning of national development". , President of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1, p. 10]. The main idea is "A new renaissance in Uzbekistan - the third renaissance" [2, p. 9]. serves to ensure its occurrence.

The emergence and successful passage of the third renaissance period in our country depends, first of all, on having a properly coordinated mechanism of the education system, on further improving the national model of training qualified students, and on the formation of highly qualified specialists. The responsibility for this falls on HEIs, which are an important part of national development. The activity of higher education institutions - the system of education and personnel training determines the level of formation and development of professional competence based on knowledge, skills, qualifications and education in the future student.

The methodology of teaching the relevant expertise in the field of psychology taught at the higher education institution operating in the field of pedagogy takes its own place. It is this subject that introduces the future teacher to the method of establishing education in the framework of continuous education, to the educational result in the relevant subject, to guarantee quality and efficiency, and to the didactic process. Also, it creates a "foundation" for acquiring the quality of professional competence that allows for the development of pedagogical activity.

Before talking about the methodology of history teaching and its improvement, it is necessary to know the dictionary meaning of the concepts "methodology", "teaching methodology", "technical teaching methodology".

According to the source, the term "methodology" is lexically "a method and a combination of methods used to do something practically" [3, p. 8].; "a system of rules, a description of the methodology for teaching or doing some kind of work" [3, p. 9].; "a type of "method", algorithm, method of carrying out a certain directed action" [4, p. 11]. means

For example, according to N. Muslimov, O'. Asqapova, M. Usmonboeva, D. Kayfupov, Kh. Pahmatova, and other scientists, the concept of "methodology" is based on: 1) a method of carrying out a task directed to a certain goal; 2) to reveal the essence, importance, practical value, technical aspect of the language used in the pedagogical field [6, p. 125].; a set of methods and methods for carrying out a task according to the purpose [7, p. 311]. is understood as such.

Also, O'.M. Asqarova and M.H. Usmonboeva argue that it is appropriate to pay attention to the etymology of the term "methodology" in order to understand its meaning. according to them, the suffix "ika" (eka, tika, dika, teka) in Greek means "bundle", "collection", "summary", "summary". For example, the Library is a collection of "Bibles" (accumulator); audio library - a collection of audio recordings (collector); video library - a collection of video clips (collector); pharmacy - a storehouse, collection (collector) of medicines available according to a prescription; disco - a set (sum) of discs (circle, dots). In addition, from a lexical point of view, the concept "methodology" means "set of methods, summary". From a purely theoretical point of view, methodology does not mean only a set of methods used in the organization of a certain activity, but also represents a form, method, object, and a set of three [8, p. 17].

For example, M.T. Studeniki's "Methodology - improvement of teaching and its organization, as well as determining the effective factor in teaching" [9, p. 4]. closes attention to the fact that.

It should be noted that this is the opinion of the author. In fact, the methodology finds the form, method, voice, tool, and also from the set of technologies that are considered to be the most effective in fulfilling a given task, as well as based on today's demand.

The concept of "teaching methodology" is derived from the combination of the terms teaching and methodology and, as understood, represents the form, method, medium, tool and technology, the way of using the method, which ensures the comprehensive teaching of a specific subject. Our opinion is also confirmed by the content of the definition given by the researcher to the concept of "teaching (or education) methodology". For example, the teaching methodology is a pedagogical science that researches the world of education in order to ensure that it reaches many people, and it includes the method, rules and requirements of education [10, p. 27].

Although the formation of the concept of speaking "methodology" and related to it "teaching methodology" and the process of its introduction to the language community are related to the ancient Heptian period, however, a unified definition of the language has not yet been reached. In our opinion, this is due to the uniqueness of the subject to be performed and taught, the complete expression of the goal, and the diversity of the direction. In general, on the basis of the "teaching methodology", "the method of starting the teaching-learning activity of the teacher, which is closed to teaching and organized by the students, to solve the didactic task, which is closed to mastering the studied material, the method of establishing the related activities of the teacher and the learner, directed to solving the educational task ; the method of organizing the student's cognitive activity" [9, p. 3]. it works.

In the source, it is said that the teaching methodology is not autonomous, but depends on a set of several fans. In particular, the teaching methodology relies on

"pedagogy, psychology and linguistics". Pedagogical science also deals with teaching methodology. however, if pedagogy studies teaching as a whole, in general, the methodology will focus on the comprehensive teaching of a specific subject. In other words, the teaching of human science takes a conceptual approach from pedagogy and studies the student's attitude towards teaching the relevant subject.

After studying the basic strength, structure and condition of the personality of the science of psychology, the teaching methodology will determine which part of the system to use and which part to use in the field of education.

Linguistics is the science of language that provides the expression of symbolic meaning, methodology accepts and applies this theoretical knowledge. Therefore, in the field of education, first of all, oral and written speech is used" [12, p. 11].

As noted above, the teaching methodology serves to close the general description of the training of a full-time fanlap in many educational events. The methodology of teaching on the topic of the topic serves to close the content of the pedagogical activity, based on the uniqueness of the relevant subject, its important characteristics, the objective (by the subject) and the partial (by the topic).

In the source, the purpose of the subject "History Teaching Methodology" is fully expressed, but it is clear that this subject shows a practical aspect. In some sources, the general pedagogical purpose is stated as the purpose of the subject "History Teaching Methodology". For example, the purpose of the methodology of teaching the subject of tapish at the higher education conference in the educational complex made by A.R. Rahmatullaeva "To serve to improve the effectiveness of tapish education by combining the methodology of teaching history with the traditional and non-traditional methods of education, methods, forms, vocabulary, organization of the educational system. " [13, p. 4]. that is multiplied.

Also, T.N. Glazipina defines the concept of teaching and expresses the goal of the most relevant science as follows: Methodology of teaching history is a pedagogical science that studies the teaching of history in order to increase its effectiveness, and its

goal is to train the future teacher in the field of education in the educational institution of the history and social sciences. It is based on the determination of the legality of training and the definition of the qualification of teaching, in particular, historical thinking, the formation of basic competence quality [14, p. 5].

Well-known pedagogues - V.V.Shogan, E.V.Stopojakova, supplementing the opinion of T.N.Glazipina, define the concept as follows: Methodology of teaching history is a pedagogical science at the core of the task, content and methodology of teaching. studies and researches the legality of teaching [15, p. 9].

In our opinion, the concept of "History teaching methodology" can be interpreted in two different ways. Second, "Methodology of History Teaching" is actually a pedagogical science, which researches the path of promising development in this subject, based on the unique characteristics of history science. Secondly, the methodology of teaching history, which is an independent direction of pedagogical activity, expresses the content of the history teacher's personal position on the organization of the "tropism" of teaching and learning in the framework of the continuous education system.

"Methodology of history teaching" is a subject that solves certain tasks like all subjects. It is in line with the purpose of keeping in mind that the subject "History Teaching Methodology" serves, firstly, for students, and secondly, for practitioners-teachers. Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account the unit of the educational program when determining the tasks.

If the subject is a student, then the following tasks will be solved on the basis of the "History Teaching Methodology" subject: "To introduce the student to the structural structure and content of the history teaching methodology, to equip the future teacher with modern knowledge of the theoretical aspects of the history teaching methodology and alternative approaches used in teaching history." , formation of practical skills and competence necessary for high level of competence in teaching history to students; instilling in students the sense of national consciousness and

patriotism, as well as preparing students to master the skills of objectively explaining the evidence related to historical events, events, and modern society, ensuring the understanding of the demands placed on modern pedagogues by the future teacher, developing students in many ways, working independently, self- developing the ability to improve oneself" [15, p. 9].

However, if the subject "History teaching methodology" serves for the practitioner-pedagogue, then the following pedagogical tasks are required to be positively resolved: the history teacher "the scientific study of the methodology of history teaching, the historian pedagogue the method, form, context and technology of history education" get acquainted with; preparing the study guide, comprehensively searching for theoretical and methodological information, collecting didactic materials for theoretical and practical training and preparing the syllabus; developing didactic development for theoretical and practical training, as well as determining the set of educational tasks and forming a set of educational tasks; formation of the qualification for the preparation of the worksheet for the study paper for the final, final and final examination of all educational subjects [13, p. 4].

In the teaching of science, "taking into account the student's educational needs, age and individual abilities of the student, determining the specific educational and developmental task of the course, applying the basic form of organizing educational activities; planning and methodologically ensuring the organization of educational training in the form of a chapter on the educational program; monitoring, analysis and evaluation of the student's level of education, development and training; to have the qualification of positive research approach to pedagogical activity" [16, p. 4]. opportunity is provided.

Pedagogical scientist F. G Tupsunov interprets the concept of "teaching methodology" in the context of teaching the science of law as follows: the methodology of teaching the science of law is the direction of the activity of the student, the essence of the concept of world development, the choice of the subject, taking into account the demands placed on the legal competence of the future student, and the selection of the

subject will lead the student to practical and practical activities. educational science that serves to improve the quality of legal education, to improve the quality of education, to improve the form, method, medium and technology of education [17, p. 22].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS: In the framework of the formation of the innovative educational environment, the practice of teaching digital science in Uzbekistan has been growing ever since. Therefore, the modern concept, teaching and learning, formed in the global information field and the innovative educational environment, require the introduction of self-explanatory science into the teaching content of science and technology. The content of the methodology of teaching tapish in Uzbekistan, the guiding principle, the guiding principle, legal requirements, methodological support, the organizational-methodical guide to the organization of the course on the subject of tapish A. Asqapov, R. Mamajonova, O. Mansypov, A. Sagdiev, T. Toshpolatov, S. Toraev , G. Fyzailova, T. Egambepdieva, Y. Gaffopov, M. Hasanova, etc. have researched the different aspects of the education of a creative personality, the quality of creativity in a teacher, student and teacher.

A.A. Vagin, E.E. Vyazemsky, P.V. Gora, A.B. Golovatenko, V.P. Gyskov, N.G. Dairi, A.G. Koloskova, G.A. Kylagina, I. Ya. Lerner, B. It was studied by such researchers as B. Mann, I. Z. Ozersky, N. L. Pomerantseva, A. I. Strajev, O. Yu. Stpelova, M. T. Ctydenikin, A.I. Chernov, K. I. Jaspers. The method of teaching history in the educational school, the method of solving the problem and the method that ensures the development of knowledge, the organization of a special program on the science of history in the classroom and outside the classroom, the presentation of the history paper in the school theater, the organization of the science week and month on the science of history, in the teaching of the science of history The use of didactic games was studied, V.T.Agaev, A.I.Vdovin, A.Yu.Golovatenko, T.V.Karpenkova, A.V.Remnev, E.V.Slominckaya, K.Umbpajko, K.A Ushmaeva, A.P. Shevyrev and others in their research on improving the efficiency of teaching history in higher

education institutions, developing students' creative thinking ability and learning activity in history classes, the prospects of history teaching, a new approach to the organization of education in the field of history, the solution to the problem is closed.

Conceptual foundations of history teaching methodology in educational institutions in developed foreign countries, socio-didactic demand for improvement of history teaching methodology, ways to satisfy it, national character and current situation of history teaching in different foreign countries, interest in learning historical knowledge among pupils and students, historical thinking and critical thinking effective factors of skill development Bhuvan Garg (Bhuvan Garg), Daniel J. Tew (Daniel J. Tew), Joyce Appleby (Joyce Appleby), Lynn Hunt (Lynn Hunt), Margaret Jacob (Margaret Jacob) and others studied the psychological, pedagogical and social aspects of the issues of raising a creative person.

It should also be noted that the methodology of teaching physical sciences is an integrated (summarizing the performance of several related disciplines, summarizing important aspects) science. For example, the methodology of teaching the science of law includes "Constitutional law", "Civil law", "Labor law", "Family law", "Criminal law", "Civil law", "Ecological law", "Economic law", "International It is possible to increase the way to create a comprehensive and significant methodical support by harmonizing the individual strengths of such disciplines as "law".

The science of the methodology of teaching science fiction is a topic for the education of future pedagogues. In today's world, science is essentially preparing many future pedagogues to work with students. In today's world, it is very important to develop the ability of students to search for new, important and useful information, to process it, to process it and to present it to the students as an educational project, to make full use of computer and multimedia technology in teaching, and to use modern educational tools.

The practice increased the fact that the method of teaching physical science is equally important for both pedagogues and students. On the other hand, this subject

serves as a methodical textbook for a young, staged or completely inexperienced pedagogue. On the other hand, eca introduces the student to the general nature of the teaching method, organizational and methodological aspect. In the field of science, the student should fully understand the nature of the teacher's pedagogical and student's educational activities, psychologically control the student, determine the educational goals and objectives, choose the appropriate form, method, medium, technology of teaching, as well as the method and method for evaluating the level of the student's mastery, form the study plan. , the competence of providing methodical support for each topic, conflicting situations that arise in the field of education, and solving problems rationally.

Based on the stated opinion and taking into account the object of research, the following explanation can be given to the concept of "methodology of teaching history (or the subject of tapix): the methodology of teaching history (or the subject of tapix) is cognitive, empirical and psychological preparation of the student for pedagogical activity in the educational process, and therefore methodological training subject that ensures the quality and comprehensiveness of the development of competence, the teaching of the science of history. This subject is part of the field of study, and the necessary competence for a history teacher is professional knowledge, historical materials (manuscripts, archival materials, historical documents, memoirs, chronicles, monographs and scientific articles on historical topics, "people's books", "oral records") and teaching materials (educational literature, general historical documents) , working with a dictionary of historical terms, a museum exhibit, an item found during archaeological excavations, a cultural monument covering national history - value; ability to analyze and summarize, critical-creative thinking, strong memory, professional competence; improves the quality of social activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The science of teaching methodology of history does not reflect the teaching principle that is suitable for today. In this principle, students are introduced to the didactic possibilities of innovative, modular,

collaborative, problem-solving, interactive, project, spatial, developmental, computer, digital, stratified individual and independent learning group, game technology. As a result, the student is actively engaged in professional practice and conducting scientific research. In addition, the ability to implement creative projects, to increase collective activity, and to exchange ideas among themselves will be developed. Маълумки, ҳар бир ўқув фани аниқ мақсадни кўзлайди. Мақсад негизида фаннинг когнитив, дидактик ва эмпирик имкониятини баҳолаш мумкин бўлади. Шу нуқтаи назардан тарих (ёки тарих фанлари)ни ўқитиш методикаси ҳам аниқ мақсадга эришишга хизмат қилади.

The method of teaching history represents the principle of successful teaching of history to students, didactic study, teaching method, providing information on modern form, method, object, technology, ensuring that students have the quality of professional competence, and preparing them for professional activity.

In this study, **the following educational tasks are solved:** to identify an innovative form, method, voice, and technology to increase the teaching capacity; basic factors: the subject to be studied, the quality of the educational material (fluency, efficiency), the student's activity level, the ability to perform practical tasks, and the ability to work effectively, choosing the educational material; get to know additional resources and enrich educational resources; in this case, to study the three-dimensionality of the method of analysis and synthesizing; formation of methodological support based on existing educational materials; improving the quality of the data in the formed methodical support package; development of professional competence in students; assessment and assessment of mastery level.

Theoretical study has shown that **the way to fully teach the science of history** is as follows: to strengthen the teaching and material teaching of the history faculty; equipping educational auditory field with modern equipment, innovative technology; ensuring that training sessions are conducted by highly competent pedagogues; providing methodological support for the teaching process; developing the student's

intellectual skills; fostering educational partnership between teacher and student; appropriate and effective use of museums, historical-cultural monuments, places and objects of historical importance in the educational environment; Involving the students of the Faculty of Arts in the active development of archeological excavations, archeological-cultural expeditions, museums, archival, touristic agencies and workshops, creating a framework for increasing their activities as volunteers or employees.

It is in accordance with the goal to pay attention to the content and direction of tourism work, such as natural, historical, cultural-historical, historical, medical-historical, heroic-patriotic, while involving students in tourism-tourism activities and agency activities.

The object of the study was the improvement of the history teaching methodology in the innovative educational environment. Based on this, the concept of "**improving the methodology of teaching history in an innovative educational environment**" should also be described in detail. Based on the results of theoretical and practical study of the problem, the concept can be defined as follows: improvement of the methodology of teaching history in an innovative educational environment - taking into account the fundamental changes taking place in the system, the modern achievements of national pedagogy, and the formation of methodological support that ensures the high-quality and comprehensive organization of educational training on the subject of history in higher education institutions. the result of closed scientific-pedagogical activities.

In the improvement of the teaching methodology in the innovative educational environment, the aim is to choose an innovative form, method, medium and technology suitable for the full course of teaching, and to enrich the curriculum.

In addition to this goal, there are several tasks that ensure successful, interesting and lively teaching of history: selection and preparation of teaching forms, methods, materials and technologies; developing methodical development in didactic teaching;

enrichment of methodological support based on a creative approach; ensuring consistent, comprehensive use of methodical support in educational practice; in the implementation of methodological support, it was defined as the assessment and evaluation of the student's level of mastery.

In the course of the preliminary experiment, it was made sure that the interactive method and the computer laptop can ensure the effectiveness of history teaching in the existing environment, with a systematic analysis of the selected problem, student learning, and professional activities of the pedagogue. Therefore, an interactive method and a computer were chosen as factors that ensure the quality and effectiveness of history teaching.

In the course of the research, educational training is carried out using visual and problem-solving techniques; listening to a conversation, lecture or conversation, discussion, getting to know historical sources and solving the problem, solving didactic problems and learning puzzles, learning the results of scientific research, learning the results of the research, as well as learning exercises (lecture and discussion); It was organized in the form of didactic games, solving problems on the analytical paper, and practical exercises aimed at solving non-standard problems.

Маълумки, талабаларнинг билимларни ўзлаштириш даражаси семинар ва амалий машғулотларда аниқланади. Шу билан бирга талабалар томонидан “Ўзбекистонда давлатчилик тарихи” фани ўзлаштириш даражасини аниқлаш ва баҳолашда назорат ишлари ҳам алоҳида ўрин тутди. Шу сабабли, тадқиқот даврида назорат ишларининг шаклини танлашга ҳам эътибор қаратилди.

Completing the didactic game of the respondent-student, creating a dictionary of historical terms, solving a learning puzzle, creating a multiplication table and an expert's opinion on the student's essay, project presentation, general memorization of physical information, morphological, conceptual and classification table on specific topics, cluster, synthesizing diagram, creating a comparative table, comparing the

historical map, solving the random problem, and so on, the expected result was achieved.

Effective as a comprehensive method for teaching history, including "Take all factors into account!" (BOHO), "Categorization", "Morphological box", "Perceptual condition" ("Mental condition"), "Thesis-organizer", "Blitz-survey", "I know. I want to know. I learned" (BBB) was selected methodically and the link was used wisely. With this, "Visual chronotope" was accepted by the dicceptant as a scientific development.

In the course of the research, the method of teaching history, which is important in the organization of education, was also identified. They include: computer keyboard, computer desktop (Power Point, Hot Potatoes, MyTestXPro), interactive dock, slide projector, television, mobile phone, social (including Telegram social thread) and Internet puzzle, historical and cultural monument, museum, object of physical significance. and addressing activities.

"Case-study" and game technology (didactic game) were chosen as technologies that serve to increase the efficiency of teaching the science of history.

T.N. Glazirina, student mastering the subject "History of Statehood in Uzbekistan" by T.N. Glazirina [18, p. 80]. based on the approach of cognitive, empirical-operational and valuable-reflective criterion. The level multiplier is B. Bloom's taxonomy [19, p. 43]. was defined as high (analysis, synthesis, evaluation), medium (understanding, application) and low (knowledge).

Much of history science cannot develop autonomously. Literature, art, geography, ethnography, archeology, sociology, religion, cultural studies and dozens of other fields interact and develop together. In general, each field has its own history of formation and development, and the historical approach is important in its study.

Improvement of the methodology of history teaching takes place on the basis of certain principles. It is known that the principle is the leading theoretical idea that

determines the essence of any activity, and leads to the provision of coherence, consistency and regularity between its purpose and result.

In addition to the general didactic principle (openness of education, interdisciplinarity, taking into account the age, psychological and personal characteristics of students in teaching, individual approach to them when assigning tasks) along with the general didactic principle (openness of education, interdisciplinarity, taking into account the student's age, psychological and personal characteristics in teaching, individual approach to them when assigning tasks) it was found that the following principle is important in improving the methodology of teaching history (1 - picture).

Figure 1. Priority principles of improvement of history teaching methodology

1. The principle of concentricity. This principle refers to repeatedly referring to a particular source. The advantage of the principle of concentricity is that it does not allow to consolidate previously learned knowledge based on repetition. Although the source is repeated several times, it is sometimes approached in a different way. A question can be posed directly, but a new, unexplored aspect is accepted for the analysis of the problem. The consistent application of the principle of concentricity serves to

strengthen the memory of the student and the thorough assimilation of historical knowledge by the student.

2. The principle of methodological pluralism [20, p. 80]. This principle, which is a specific form of epistemological pluralism, refers to the approach to historical events and people based on the diversity of thought in the teaching process. Consequently, students' knowledge, outlook, and life experiences differ from each other. Naturally, historical events and processes are also interpreted differently by them. The principle of methodological pluralism in the teaching process shows that there are several or many independent positions in relation to the basis. The provision of this principle will improve the thinking ability of the students. Teachers to express his attitude towards the views and approaches of his peers. But in this process, the pedagogue's patience is required. Because the diversity of ideas should lead to the discovery of the true essence of the methodological basis.

3. The principle of regularity, consistency and systematicity. As in school, lyceum and college education, the principle of regularity, consistency and systematization keeps the development of the history of the beginning to the present day in the content of the science of history, step by step. Regularity and consistency serve for the complete understanding of the step by step learning of each step in the lesson plan and the next step based on the learned step. Systematicity requires the student to study the history of the nation and the world in the form of interrelated and interrelated elements.

4. The principle of priority of scientific and theoretical knowledge. It is necessary to cover the historical events, incidents and events in detail. Therefore, it is only then that they can be evaluated objectively and correctly. Introducing the student to historical knowledge that is not supported by scientific evidence will lead to misunderstandings. In the teaching of historical sciences, relying on evidence found in scientific research does not accustom students to a responsible, serious approach to historical sources. After all, wrongly closing the historical evidence, biased

interpretation and analysis means disrespect for the past of the nation, the people, the ancestors, and lack of confidence in the future.

Historical sciences have turned into social sciences, and they rely on the scientific method of explanation. In addition, it is necessary to pay special attention of the pedagogue to the theoretically correct interpretation of the historical information and evidence of the students in the course of history. This requires not only the pedagogue, but also the student to have oral and written communication skills, a good culture and communication skills. The student should simply describe the study material on the topic being studied. It is important to have an analytical, critical, creative and creative approach to learning. Only then will the student's ability to think develop, and the worldview will be enriched.

5. The principle of historicity and succession. Historically, as well as leader (leaders) - people's heroes, state and political figures, spiritual leaders, military commanders, historical events, events and processes in the life of humanity, a certain nation, evaluating the behavior and activities of the military leader from the point of view of the era, giving an objective assessment if it is carried out on the basis of the principle of historicity, then loyalty to the values - national traditions, customs and traditions passed down by ancestors is manifested on the basis of the principle of inheritance. At the same time, the principle of succession also means that the right to the national wealth and heritage created by the ancestors belongs to the descendants. In this regard, it is important to be able to connect the morals and manners of the spiritual traditions preserved in the middle of the century, which are important for the present era, with the traditions of other peoples, to raise the religion to a higher level by relying on the past, and to ensure continuous communication and connection in the religion. ” [20, p. 108] should be taken into account.

6. The principle of hermeneutic approach. This principle serves to interpret historical terms, to transfer them from one field of science to another field of science, to explain the essence of the text that illuminates historical events. According to M.F.

Rumyantseva, a historian studying a historical source interprets its essence from the point of view of his position. In other words, the hermeneutic approach does not reflect the attitude of the future historian as a subject to the object or subject of historical knowledge. This principle allows the historian to understand the content of historical sources based on the approach of the researcher, to understand oneself in the process [20, p. 31].

Thus, the formation of an innovative educational environment requires the implementation of a radical change in the educational system as well as in Japan. The formation of methodological support that ensures the quality and comprehensive organization of educational training in the field of history at the Higher Education Institution, the improvement of the methodology of teaching in the innovative educational environment, requires taking into account the fundamental changes taking place in the system, the modern achievements of local and national pedagogy. In the process of improvement, innovative forms, methods, materials, and technologies are selected that are suitable for the complete process of teaching. Special attention was paid to the selection of an interactive method and a computer laptop, which are important in improving the methodology of history teaching. As a result of this, the educational training organized on the subject "History of Statehood in Uzbekistan" was made interesting and comprehensive.

Innovative form of education

Types of lectures	Types of seminars	Types of practical training courses	Types of control
Information-lecture, problem report, Visual lecture,	Seminar-conversation Seminar based on listening and discussion of lectures and abstracts	Practical training combined with a didactic game A practical exercise based on a role-playing game	Playing a didactic game puzzle Creating a glossary of technical terms Solve the learning problem

online lecture, binary speech, Webinar lecture, Lecture based on errors, Lecture- conference Lecture- advice	Mixed seminar (lecture and discussion) Seminar-discussion A seminar aimed at familiarizing with historical sources and interpreting them A seminar based on didactic tasks and solving puzzles The results of scientific researches are closely related to learning A seminar based on solving learning problems Seminar-excursion Seminar-collective Seminar-round table	A practical exercise adapted to the business game Training-practical training An exercise designed to complete the task in the analytical paper Practical training for solving non- standard tests	Project presentation, expert reviewer, A guide to memorizing a historical story, creating a student essay Morphological, classificatory conceptual and tabular; creation of a perception map, cluster, synthesis- diagram, cross- tabulation Check historical records Solving graded tests ва жадвал; идрок хари-таси, кластер, синтез- диаграмма, қиёсий жадвалларни тузи
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CONCLUSION: Global globalization and the formation of innovative educational environment, in turn, brought to the fore the need to improve the education system, taking into account the revolutionary change that is taking place in the field of science, technology, technology and development. The demand for training also requires the improvement of the teaching methodology.

Judicious and reasonable resolution of organizational issues in teaching science based on the needs of the educational material ensures the successful completion of the education process. The organizational aspect of teaching is determined by education, the set didactic task and the content of the educational material, the content of the educational material, and the rational choice of the material.

The uniqueness and nature of historical sciences requires the selection of problematic, developmental, project, computer, spatial, collaborative, interactive, innovative and modular, as well as game-oriented types of education, as well as the innovative form of teaching and effective use of the didactic capabilities of the system.

However, most pedagogues have superficial knowledge about innovative educational technology. The selection of the innovative educational technology, taking into account the scope of the studied topic, the level of creativity and learning activity of the student, does not give the expected result. During the research, a special methodology for improving the methodology of history teaching in the field of "History of Uzbek statehood" was created.

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